

**Employability skills in people affected by neurodegenerative disorders:
a scoping review**

1. Research question(s)

How employability skills can be increased in people affected by neurodegenerative disorders?

2. Methodology

- Type of review = scoping review to map out an area of study that may not have been reviewed comprehensively with the aim of informing future education programs, practice and research → PRISMA guidelines for scoping reviews
- Search engines = PubMed/MEDLINE[§], PsycINFO (via OVID)*, Scopus, Web of Science
- Population of interest = People with Parkinson's disease, Multiple Sclerosis, Huntington's disease

3. Other potentially interesting works

- Koerts J et al. Working capacity of patients with Parkinson's disease - A systematic review. *Parkinsonism Relat Disord.* 2016 Jun;27:9-24. doi: 10.1016/j.parkreldis.2016.03.017.
- Dorstyn DS et al. Employment and multiple sclerosis: A meta-analytic review of psychological correlates. *J Health Psychol.* 2019 Jan;24(1):38-51. doi: 10.1177/1359105317691587.
- van der Zwaan KF et al. Huntington's disease influences employment before and during clinical manifestation: A systematic review. *Parkinsonism Relat Disord.* 2022 Mar;96:100-108. doi: 10.1016/j.parkreldis.2022.02.022.
- Vitturi BK et al. Work Barriers and Job Adjustments of People with Multiple Sclerosis: A Systematic Review. *J Occup Rehabil.* 2023 Sep;33(3):450-462. doi: 10.1007/s10926-022-10084-1.

§PubMed/MEDLINE

Search terms	
<p>(employability OR "employability skills" OR "graduates employability" OR "perceived employability" OR "enhancing employability" OR "professional integration" OR "career development" OR "workplace learning" OR "professional competences" OR "work engagement" OR "career success" OR "daily engagement" OR job security OR "job retention" OR "continue working" OR return to work OR "career employability" [tiab:~0] OR "attractiveness employability" [tiab:~0] OR "employability career" [tiab:~0] OR "competence-based employability" [tiab:~0]) AND ("neurodegenerative disorders" OR neurodegenerative diseases OR Parkinson disease OR "Parkinson's disease" OR multiple sclerosis)</p>	
<p>("employability"[All Fields] OR "employable"[All Fields] OR "employer"[All Fields] OR "employer s"[All Fields] OR "employers"[All Fields] OR "employment"[MeSH Terms] OR "employment"[All Fields] OR "employments"[All Fields] OR "employability skills"[All Fields] OR "graduates employability"[All Fields] OR "perceived employability"[All Fields] OR "enhancing employability"[All Fields] OR "professional integration"[All Fields] OR "career development"[All Fields] OR "workplace learning"[All Fields] OR "professional competences"[All Fields] OR "work engagement"[All Fields] OR "career success"[All Fields] OR "daily engagement"[All Fields] OR ("job security"[MeSH Terms] OR ("job"[All Fields] AND "security"[All Fields])) OR "job security"[All Fields]) OR "job retention"[All Fields] OR "continue working"[All Fields] OR ("return to work"[MeSH Terms] OR ("return"[All Fields] AND "work"[All Fields])) OR "return to work"[All Fields]) OR "career employability"[Title/Abstract:~0] OR "attractiveness employability"[Title/Abstract:~0] OR "employability career"[Title/Abstract:~0] OR "competence-based employability"[Title/Abstract:~0]) AND ("neurodegenerative disorders"[All Fields] OR ("neurodegenerative diseases"[MeSH Terms] OR ("neurodegenerative"[All Fields] AND "diseases"[All Fields])) OR "neurodegenerative diseases"[All Fields]) OR ("parkinson disease"[MeSH Terms] OR ("parkinson"[All Fields] AND "disease"[All Fields])) OR "parkinson disease"[All Fields] OR "Parkinson's disease"[All Fields] OR ("multiple sclerosis"[MeSH Terms] OR ("multiple"[All Fields] AND "sclerosis"[All Fields])) OR "multiple sclerosis"[All Fields]))</p>	

*APA PsycInfo

Search terms	
1	exp Employability/ or (Employability or Employment or Employer or Employment status or Employment dissatisfaction or employment history or Employment problem finding or Employment Supported or employment discrimination or Employment Termination or employment tests or Sheltered employment or Employment issues or employer conflict or Employment education or Employment Processes or Employer Attitudes or Employer in work related accident or employment service or full employment or employer liability or Employment environmental intervention or employment unemployment or Self employed or "Encounter due to Pre employment examination" or Work Engagement or "Return to Work" or enhancing employability).mp.
2	exp Parkinson's Disease/ or (Parkinson Disease or Parkinson Disease Gene Mutation Reagents or Parkinsonism Juvenile or Juvenile Parkinson Disease Gene Mutation Reagents or Parkinson Tremor Disease Gene Mutation Reagents or Familial Parkinson Disease Type 1 Gene Mutation Reagents or Parkin Type Juvenile Parkinson Disease Gene Mutation Reagents or IVD Panels Human Genetics Neurodegenerative Disorder Parkinson or Parkinson disease without dyskinesia or IVD Panels Human Genetics Neurodegenerative Disorder Parkinson Mutation or IVD Panels Human Genetics Neurodegenerative Disorder Parkinson Del Dup or Parkinson disease with dyskinesia with fluctuations or Parkinson disease without dyskinesia with fluctuations or Parkinson disease with dyskinesia without fluctuations or "Parkinson's disease and parkinsonism" or "Idiopathic Parkinsonism or Parkinson's disease" or "Primary Parkinsonism or Parkinson's disease").mp.
3	exp Multiple Sclerosis/ or (Multiple Sclerosis or Multiple sclerosis aggravated or Multiple Sclerosis Chronic Progressive or Tumefactive multiple sclerosis or sclerosis brain multiple or psychosis multiple sclerosis or Disseminated multiple sclerosis or Multiple Sclerosis Relapsing Remitting or Multiple Sclerosis Progressive Relapsing or Multiple Sclerosis Secondary Progressive or Multiple Sclerosis Primary Progressive or Multiple sclerosis pseudo relapse).mp.
4	2 or 3
5	1 and 4

***Scopus**

Search terms	
1	(TITLE-ABS-KEY ('daily AND engagement') OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ('job AND retention') OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ('continue AND working') OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ('return AND to AND work') OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ('work AND engagement') OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ('employment') OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ('vocational AND rehabilitation') OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ('employee AND retention') OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ('job AND satisfaction') OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ('return AND to AND work') AND TITLE-ABS-KEY (neurodegenerative AND disorders) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (neurodegenerative AND diseases))
2	(TITLE-ABS-KEY (parkinson AND disease) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (parkinson's AND disease) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY (multiple AND sclerosis) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Parkinson Disease Gene Mutation Reagents ") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Parkinsonism Juvenile") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Juvenile Parkinson Disease Gene Mutation Reagents ") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Parkinson Tremor Disease Gene Mutation Reagents ") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Familial Parkinson Disease Type 1 Gene Mutation Reagents ") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Parkin Type Juvenile Parkinson Disease Gene Mutation Reagents ") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("IVD Panels Human Genetics Neurodegenerative Disorder Parkinson ") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Multiple sclerosis aggravated ") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Multiple Sclerosis Chronic Progressive ") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Tumefactive multiple sclerosis ") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("sclerosis brain multiple ") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Multiple Sclerosis Relapsing Remitting") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Multiple Sclerosis Progressive Relapsing ") OR TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Multiple Sclerosis Secondary Progressive"))
3	1 and 2

***Web of science**

Search terms	
1	((((ALL=("Employment")) OR ALL=(Employer)) OR ALL=("Employment status ")) OR ALL=("Employment dissatisfaction ")) OR ALL=("employment history") and Vocational Rehabilitation (Should – Search within topic) and Employability (Should – Search within topic) and Self-employment (Should – Search within topic) and Labour Market (Should – Search within topic) and Employers (Should – Search within topic) and Unemployment (Should – Search within topic)
2	((((((((((ALL=("Parkinson Disease")) OR ALL=("Parkinson Disease Gene Mutation Reagents ")) OR ALL=("Parkinsonism Juvenile")) OR ALL=("Juvenile Parkinson Disease Gene Mutation Reagents ")) OR ALL=("Parkinson Tremor Disease Gene Mutation Reagents ")) OR ALL=("Familial Parkinson Disease Type 1 Gene Mutation Reagents")) OR ALL=("Parkin Type Juvenile Parkinson Disease Gene Mutation Reagents")) OR ALL=("IVD Panels Human Genetics Neurodegenerative Disorder Parkinson ")) OR ALL=("Parkinson disease without dyskinesia ")) OR ALL=("IVD Panels Human Genetics Neurodegenerative Disorder Parkinson Mutation ")) OR ALL=("IVD Panels Human Genetics Neurodegenerative Disorder Parkinson Del Dup")
3	((((((((((ALL=("Multiple Sclerosis ")) OR ALL=("Multiple sclerosis aggravated ")) OR ALL=("Multiple Sclerosis Chronic Progressive ")) OR ALL=("Tumefactive multiple sclerosis ")) OR ALL=("sclerosis brain multiple ")) OR ALL=("psychosis multiple sclerosis")) OR ALL=("Disseminated multiple sclerosis ")) OR ALL=("Multiple Sclerosis Relapsing Remitting")) OR ALL=("Multiple Sclerosis Progressive Relapsing ")) OR ALL=("Multiple Sclerosis Secondary Progressive")) OR ALL=("Multiple Sclerosis Primary Progressive ")) OR ALL=("Multiple sclerosis pseudo relapse")
4	2 and 3
5	1 and 4

***Web of science**

Search terms	
1	(ALL=('Daily engagement') OR ALL=('Job retention') OR ALL=('Continue working') OR ALL=('return to work') OR ALL=('work engament') OR (QMTS=("RETURN-TO-WORK")) OR (QMTS=("EMPLOYMENT")) OR (QMTS=("VOCATIONAL REHABILITATION")) OR (QMTS=("EMPLOYEE RETENTION")) OR (QMTS=("JOB SATISFACTION")) OR (QMTS=("RETURN TO WORK"))
2	((((((((((ALL=("Parkinson Disease")) OR ALL=("Parkinson Disease Gene Mutation Reagents ")) OR ALL=("Parkinsonism Juvenile")) OR ALL=("Juvenile Parkinson Disease Gene Mutation Reagents ")) OR ALL=("Parkinson Tremor Disease Gene Mutation Reagents ")) OR ALL=("Familial Parkinson Disease Type 1 Gene Mutation Reagents")) OR ALL=("Parkin Type Juvenile Parkinson Disease Gene Mutation Reagents")) OR ALL=("IVD Panels Human Genetics Neurodegenerative Disorder Parkinson ")) OR ALL=("Parkinson disease

	without dyskinesia ")) OR ALL=("IVD Panels Human Genetics Neurodegenerative Disorder Parkinson Mutation ") OR ALL=("IVD Panels Human Genetics Neurodegenerative Disorder Parkinson Del Dup")
3	((((((((((ALL=("Multiple Sclerosis ")) OR ALL=("Multiple sclerosis aggravated ") OR ALL=("Multiple Sclerosis Chronic Progressive ") OR ALL=("Tumefactive multiple sclerosis ") OR ALL=("sclerosis brain multiple ") OR ALL=("psychosis multiple sclerosis")) OR ALL=("Disseminated multiple sclerosis ") OR ALL=("Multiple Sclerosis Relapsing Remitting")) OR ALL=("Multiple Sclerosis Progressive Relapsing ") OR ALL=("Multiple Sclerosis Secondary Progressive")) OR ALL=("Multiple Sclerosis Primary Progressive ") OR ALL=("Multiple sclerosis pseudo relapse"))
4	2 or 3
5	1 and 4